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Shepherd Motif in Psalm 23:1-6 and Its Implications for Church Leadership and Pastoral Care in Nigeria

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Abstract

The cry of the twenty-first century Christian community is for genuine Church leaders and care givers who will not exploit, malign or neglect those who need one form of care or the other, who run to them for succor. Many people in the Church and community are experiencing spiritual, moral, financial, health, economic and psychological issues and crises that are beyond their control. The paper seeks to contribute to the body of knowledge as it underscores the significance of shepherding for Church leadership and pastoral care giving in Nigeria. Through making deductions from Johann August Ernesti's historical-grammatical method of exegesis, the findings show that, church leaders in Nigeria must keep God's injunction concerning Pastoral ministry as shepherds as they give a sense of belonging to the care seekers and exhibit care and compassion. This paper therefore through making deductions from the context of Psalm 23 concludes that the biblical model of shepherding provides a holistic view of what pastoral care by the church leadership entails. It is therefore recommended that Church leaders should be faithful to their calling, possess virtues that will aid their ministry, live a life of compassion and love as well as nurture and show concern for their flock.

Keywords: Christian, Pastoral Care, Church Leadership, Shepherding Motif, Exposition of Psalm 23:1-6

Introduction

Pastoral ministry is a ministry of proclaiming redemption or teaching the people about the kingdom of God, and much more than that, it is also the ministry of care. In Christian ministry, it is not sufficient to proclaim the gospel; there is need for a thorough practical demonstration of the importance of caring for others. People from churches in Nigeria are struggling with existential problems as secularization, lack of the meaning of life, lack of interpersonal communication and communion, spiritual and moral crisis, isolation, individualism, depression, addictions to alcohol, drugs, absence of care, and not seeing a better future out of their present predicaments, some people are contemplating suicide. Contemporary Church leaders are fast losing the sense of commitment to the ministry of care for the sheep they are leading; displaying greed, manipulation and exploitation. Johann August Ernesti's historical-grammatical method of exegesis was employed because the Bible is an ancient sacred text written within human history in the ancient world with a cultural gap that significantly differs from the twenty-first century. The method uses the history and grammar of the text to draw out the interpretation for the original and contemporary readers. This paper therefore through making deductions from the context of Psalm 23 argues that the biblical model of shepherding provides a holistic view of what pastoral care by the church leadership entails. This paper therefore discusses the art of shepherding, especially in ancient near east and its motif in Psalm 23 and thereby draws implications for Church leadership and pastoral care in the twenty-first century in Nigeria.

Shepherd Motif in Psalm 23:1-6

The word Shepherd is from the Hebrew word *ra'ah* which means "he pastured or tended" referring to those in charge of sheep (Odewole 2013:3). Shepherding in ancient Palestine is a profession. It is a unique one that requires a lot of creative imaginative skills if one will be successful at it. Porter (2001:55) noted that the nature and mechanism of carrying it out makes it prominent and requires a lot of attention and dedication. It is not an occupation that can be done half-heartedly. In order to know and understand this concept, there is need to explore the world of the bible times about the sheep and what shepherding them entails. In Bible times, most of the Patriarchs were herdsmen. The early Israelites referred to *Yahrveh* as

the God of Abraham, Isaac and Jacob, who were shepherds. That shepherding is a calling cannot be over emphasised. There are marked distinctions between shepherds with a calling and those that are hired (Stowe, 1976:19). The shepherd identifies with the sheep. If the sheep is bruised, wounded or sick, he also feels it. (20).

Psalm 23 is viewed as the work of David, which according to Asumang (2010) is a reflection of his youthful days as a shepherd (8). God chose a brave, young, shepherd named David when searching for Saul's successor. As a result of the unique role of a shepherd, the term came to be widely used symbolically in the literature of Israel and the early church. God declares Himself the shepherd of His people (Matt. 9:6, John 10:1-18). God's people are consistently referred to as His sheep (Psalm 95:7; Ps. 100:3, Is. 53:6; 1 Peter 2:25). The shepherd is also a metaphor for Jesus and a figure for leaders and ministers. Contextually speaking, the shepherding imagery is better understood within the context of the whole flock rather than an individual sheep Audirsch (2016:61). The shepherd motif is deduced with a view to bringing out the multi-faceted nature of pastoral care (Tidball, 1986, 47).

The Lord is my Shepherd, I shall not want

David introduced the reader to the role of the Lord as his Shepherd (Ross, 2001, 127). The possessive pronoun gives an understanding of what David sought to communicate throughout the rest of the chapter. God is the shepherd who takes care of him, the sheep. He is a caring loving guide to the sheep. According to Carnes (2007: 2), Sheep are often dirty and vulnerable animals that are unable to care for themselves and prone to wandering. They will follow anybody, are gullible and cannot think for themselves. He is responsible for the care and safety of the flock and one who is capable to move them from one pasture to another. His job included supervision and keeping watch over the flocks, protecting them from thieves and wild animals searching for stray sheep to devour. The shepherd is also responsible for leading the flock to adequate land for grazing and water Gentz (1986:969). At the same time, God feels a sense of ownership and responsibility for his sheep (I have everything I need). The sheep left alone and unattended are prone to die of disease or starvation and could easily fall victim to predators (Keller, 21). According to Ryken, Wilhoit and Longman (1998:785), care should not only be general but specific; the sheep must feel that the shepherd cares very much about it and that it possesses the personal attention from the shepherd.

He cause me to lie down, to rest in green pastures.

The sheep is a cloven-hoofed mammal, ruminant animal. Rumination means that this animal regurgitates its food and chews it. Keller (1970: 35) notes that at least four requirements must be met before sheep can lie down. First, they must be free of fear of the unexpected and the unknown. Then, they must be free from friction within the flock; Third, the sheep can only lie down when they are free of pests such as flies or parasites. Finally, sheep will lie down only when they are free from hunger.

He leads me beside peaceful streams.

Sheep also depend on the shepherd for water. The peaceful streams connote calmness opposed to rivers that can frighten the sheep and expose them (Poole, 1962:37). *He restores my soul vs.3* God prevents the sheep from wandering, departing, and fainting away. The soul is imparted with new life which refreshes and strengthens the sheep (Keil and Delitzsch, 1978, 330). *He leads me in the path of righteousness on account of his name vs. 3b.* Sheep are creatures of habit. When left to fend for themselves, they are prone to error so must be guided (Giles and Jerome, 1990, 102). Sheep need a shepherd to provide them a haven and a shelter from the storms of winter. Sheep need a shepherd to fulfill their needs. Sheep need a shepherd to lead them out of the fold in the freshness of the new day and to lead them along the right path, careful to avoid the dangerous path, the perilous path and the treacherous path. Sheep need a shepherd to take away their confusion, and their sense of disorientation. Sheep need a shepherd to gather them together and to return them home.

Even when I walk among the valley of the shadow of death, I will not fear evil for you are with me vs. 4.

During summer, it was common for the shepherd to take his flock from the lowlands to the high plateaus of the mountain ranges. Porter described the sheep as being timid and an animal that lacks defense mechanism against predators. The sheep cannot see more than 15 yards because of defective vision. This inability to recognize enemies except at very close range makes it easy prey for predators. When the sheep

is ill-fed, it looks for a way to satisfy its hunger thereby wandering off, and thereby ending as a prey in the hand of predator. And thus, there is need for someone to always be there to guide and care for the sheep Stowe (12). The way was often dangerous and new to the sheep. God will not only provide the basic needs, He will also provide protection from danger. Sheep need a God to watch over them while they rest peacefully in the cool shade of whispering trees and bushes, during the heat of the day.

The rod and staff comfort me

A good shepherd minds what he wears and what he eats. They know they need to stay healthy in order to discharge their duties effectively. The lives of the flock depend on this. In addition to this clothing, a shepherd also carried with him three implements or weapons: a sling shot, a stout wooden club staff and a crooked handle. These were used for protection or care of the sheep. The sling shot and stout club were used for protection of the sheep. Natural predators of sheep were lions, bears, jackals, wild dogs, and hyenas (Porter, 58). It is used as weapon and a guiding tool; for discipline and counting. Borowski (2003) noted that the staff aids in rocky terrain, and rod primarily as defense (49-50).

Sheep need a shepherd who is himself the door of the sheep-fold - who is the door leading the sheep into the fold and the door keeping out predators and strangers. And lost sheep need such a shepherd who is so concerned for the one lost sheep that he will leave the ninety and nine in the safety of the fold and go out into the wilderness to seek and to save that one which is lost, until that one lost sheep is found and restored to the flock and to the fold. They need a shepherd who will give them a sense of belonging guiding them with creative skills and imagination. This is the art required in shepherding.

You prepare a feast for me in the presence of my enemies vs. 5.

God provides food even in the midst of danger. For the shepherd to provide green pastures, he takes several advance trips to prepare by pulling out poisonous plants, to get nutritious plants that are of great value to the sheep even if it is among predators. *You fattened my head with oil.* The ancient shepherds used oil as a preventive treatment from flies, mosquitoes, gnats, and some parasites. The oil provides a soothing effect on the sheep and also leads to restoration of health. *Goodness and mercy* belongs to a well catered-for flock and well managed flock benefits the land. With watchful care and rotation, sheep can leave a pasture much better than they found it with their consumption of weeds and undesirable plants.

Church Leadership

Leadership in the Bible is viewed first as a good influence that one person has on another. A leader's first task is not to keep the machinery of an organisation moving and fulfilling its goals but to help those under him to live and serve in obedience to the will of God (Fernando, 2000: 15). Spiritual leadership is Parenthood, relating with tender loving care. It is not unhealthy quest for status or developing a possessive attitude (18). Also, Church leadership is one of the ways the minister or pastor arranges and coordinates the human and material resources of the Church to achieve her stated objectives and the divine purpose of God (Odewole, 14). There is a hierarchical 'headship' pattern of leadership demonstrated in the institutions of Old Testament Israel (Ex. 18:21), and in the New Testament, the basic reality that Scripture presents is that the Church is a living organism with Jesus Christ himself functioning as the head (Richards and Hoeldtke, 1982: 14).

Adeniji (2019) defines leadership in the Christian context as "a process whereby a Pastor motivates and influences his work-committee to use Bible-compliant skills and strategies to carry out God-given assignments until the Church or organisation is transformed" (94). The basic components of any Christian approach to leadership include character-good traits that ensure being above reproach, competency - ability to perform in an area of expertise and context- which places an individual with a position and frame of reference from which to be given a voice and a stage from which to communicate it and calling- a consistent sense of purpose, and an unrelenting passion to achieve something (Anthony and Estep Jr., 2005:350, 352). Titles given to leaders in the early church (deacon, bishop, elder and shepherd) not only depict their function (competence), but their placement in a position of responsibility and oversight for ministry (context) (351).

Adetunji (2010) defined Church leadership as all who exercise influence, guidance, and direction to those in the Church towards fulfilling the Church's goals (4). Supporting this view, Ishola (2019) affirmed that

the leadership team of the Church includes both the laity and the clergy, and that “leadership in the twenty-first century is less about employing people than empowering them; it is more about controlling people than releasing them into the service” (136). The clergy and the laity must team up to effectively harness all resources and abilities together, to achieve set goals and objectives (Ishola and Oparinde, 2017: 264). Shepherd and ranching are two elemental styles of leadership present in the church and the success of whichever style depends on the maturity level of the followers. Shepherds try to personally meet everyone’s needs while ranchers strive to care for the flocks as a whole. (356, 357). One way or the other, a good blend of these styles ensures provision of pastoral and professional oversight over the members in a congregation. Patterson (1992) added trustees, board members, committee members, directors, Superintendents, chairpersons, etc to the category of church leaders. He maintained that they must guide, direct, and influence others towards fulfilling the Church’s goals. They exercise influence, guidance, and direction to those in the Church towards fulfilling the Church’s goals (8).

According to Engstrom (1977), leaders make things happen by acting in order to help others work in an environment within which each individual serving under them finds themselves encouraged and stimulated to a point where they are helped to realize their fullest potentials (23). The responsibility of these leaders is the care and nurture of behaviours (Richards and Hoeldtke, 92). Whatever titles or tasks given to church leaders today, their common mission are an equipping, shepherding one. The management of the body is the prerogative of the head (Jesus), but the care of the members is the mission of human leaders, that the body might be healthy and responsive (92). There is a feeling element in the sensitive caring of the Christian which makes room for reason and respects the other person’s mind (Adams, 1978: 16,17).

A model of leadership developed by Ernest Mosley (1973: 12-28) and popularised by Robert Dale revolves around three interlocking circles. First, proclaim the gospel to all by means of preaching, evangelism and nurture. Second is care for the members and the community through pastoral counselling and visitation and through family ministries and grief support; and the third is leading the Church towards the achievement of its mission (Beasley-Murray, 1995: 46). These three points summarise the task of the pastoral leadership in a contemporary church. Oduleye (2015) stated that leading well encompasses the visionary, motivational, strategic, bridge building and managerial styles of leadership (57-61). The knowledge of which style and when to apply it is very important for church leaders in discharging their duties.

The Concept of Pastoral Care

Pastoral care is an unlimited, unstereotyped, practical and spiritual art of giving care to persons at the point of their needs. It is a care that reaches to the body, mind and soul. Brister (1992) noted that it arises out of the push of the pastoral calling and the pull of human need (22). Pastoral care consists of helping acts, done by representatives, aimed at healing, sustaining, guiding, and reconciliation of troubled souls (Clebsch and Jaekle (1975: 4)). Pattison (1993) described pastoral care as the activity directed towards the elimination and relief of sin and sorrow (13). Pastoral care is a response to the need that everyone has for warmth, nurture, support, and caring. Its functions include healing, sustaining, guiding, reconciling, and nurturing Clinebell (1991:43, 46). Pastors are not the only people in the church engaged in pastoral care. The pastor has a general pastoral oversight of the church, while the task of pastoral care must be rightly shared. It is a specialized form of loving, which involves the ability to listen and to discern, acting where appropriate as a channel of the grace and discipline of Christ. The pastoral load is shared with the gifted team of care-givers such as the deacons who assist in one way or another (Beasley-Murray, 1995:171-172).

Care is more meaningful and greatly appreciated when offered more than only in periods of distress, trouble or crisis (Steinbron, 1997:26). Routine visitation must be carried out from time to time. Visitation is about the ministry of presence, meant to encourage people for commitment, strength and steadfastness (Kehinde, 2014:105,107). Presence means a lot to the people and give them a sense of worth from the church leadership. Larson, Anderson and Self viewed pastoral care as a healthy relationship between a caregiver and a care seeker (1990:120). It must remain healthy and fresh. In Stowe’s views, Sunday’s care

is not enough; congregational needs may be met in a very essential way through the ministries of preaching and teaching in the congregational context but, as good as this is, it will not suffice without a complementary ministry of shepherding between Sundays (85).

The caregiver has the duty to be comprehensible on Sunday and easily accessible during the week to the parishioners. Neither area of responsibility can be neglected without endangering the spiritual life of the flock. Church leadership in being accessible may need to go and look out for the care seekers. Not all will come to them. Johnson (1953: 24) defines pastoral care as “a religious ministry to individual persons in dynamic relationships, arising from insights into individual needs and mutual discovery of potentialities for spiritual growth”. The church will do more to know when to take care of individual needs and when to take care of the congregational needs.

There are varying numbers of personal needs in any congregation and it is also in age brackets. Some are very critical while some are mild, yet none can be neglected or sidelined. With twentieth-century sophistication, most people wear their masks very well; while they are laughing on the outside, too many are crying on the inside. Others have become almost numbed by the continual pressure of their problems. Silently but desperately, they cry out for help (Stowe, 86). Wise holds the view that “pastoral care is not an adjunct to the ministry; it is the very core” (1966, 12). Pastoral care is from the cradle to the grave so the church leadership must have interest in people, know them and love them (White, 1998: 97).

Implications for Church Leadership and Pastoral Care

There is no gainsaying that the Christian ministry is a ministry of care where love and faith to care for others is practically demonstrated (Ajimatanrareje, 1997:24-25). The shepherd-sheep relationship in Psalm 23 stresses the care and compassion of the divine shepherd and the dependence of people on God to meet all their needs. The church is idealism in action as it is supposed to be made up of disciples or learners whose lives have been transformed by Jesus Christ. Therefore, in an atmosphere conducive for Christian growth and in situations of need, help will be given (Dobbins, 1960,9). The Church must be a dynamic Christian group and a beloved community which must minister to human needs. A church may be grateful to government or social service agencies for assisting in alleviating problems or rendering first aid, providing material assistance, and even to counsel those in trouble, but they cannot take the place of the Church with its compassionate ministries rendered in the name of Christ (12).

Consequent upon the analysis of Psalm 23:1-6, the issue of the lack of care for seekers by care givers (Church leaders) in Nigeria can be curtailed if they can understand the nature of the relationship that exists between the shepherd and the sheep metaphor as depicted by David in Psalm 23 and thereby imbibe the model. A care giver must give a sense of belonging to the care seekers (congregation) that will give them a feeling that they are greatly treasured, treated and cared for greatly. The relationship must be personal and individualistic. The relationship should be such that the care seeker does not desire any other care apart from that being given to him. The care giver must be “The Shepherd”. The use of “IS” connotes an ever-fresh relationship, not the type that existed before or one postponed for the future. Care must be given when it is due and the need calls for it. The care seeker should not dream of how care used to be or what it will look like but must be viewed in the light of the present time.

A pastoral care giver has the responsibility to guide by leading the care receiver in the right way and out of chaos. He must pattern his life according to the shepherding style of Christ in order to yield good fruits. He must feed and provide good nurture through the ministry of the word and sometimes physical food with skill and knowledge. The shepherd must also protect the afflicted and the healthy sheep. None must be neglected or abandoned. He must ensure that their fears are laid to rest when he counsels or meets with them. They must go back home with a settled mind, a bold and courageous one that does not look over its shoulder but is calm. They must be helped to cope with tensions and frictions with others of their kind. Parishioners must be helped to imbibe the right attitude towards social behaviour so as to be at peace in the environment they find themselves. They must be protected from dangers. They must be led in search of greener pastures. Sometimes the faith of care seekers is fragile; sometimes they are faced with temptations, danger, weariness, hunger, when forsaken and deserted. That is when they need care givers most. They cannot be neglected. They must be led to where there is nourishment and rest for their souls.

The care giver must minister to the basic needs of care seekers. Until these needs are met, care seekers are restless and vulnerable.

The shepherd-sheep relationship must be that of forming and leading a Christian community, nurturing faith with righteous discipline, guarding with loving concern, sharing the life of care receivers, and even sacrificing one's life if need be. It is the responsibility of the church leaders to shield the sheep from dangers. Shepherding is demanding and strategic and also rewarding. It requires a heart that has compassion for people, a spirit that responds to God and feet to move quickly to carry out practical ministry (Nihinlola, 2016:160). This implies that pastoral care cannot thrive where self-centredness, ignorance, slothfulness and misplaced priorities dominate (Eims, 2001, 61-65). Church leaders can only move people to action after they have moved them with emotion and will develop credibility with them when they connect and show that they genuinely care for them (Maxwell, 2007:115-116).

Pastoral care receivers often find themselves in situations that cause fear and worry, it is then that they find courage and strength in God and the church leadership (Opade, 2018:188). Providing shepherding leadership by pastoral care giver in a contemporary church must be participatory. It will require planning. Planning involves setting goals and objectives for the progress of the flock, determining where the green grass grows and the still waters lie, and discovering and guiding the sheep into the paths of truth and righteousness. It will also require organisation; bringing the sheep together as a flock or congregation, teaching and helping them to live, learn, love and labour together in God's vineyard. He will also care for them, guide, protect and lead them to green pastures where they can be refreshed and strengthened in their Christian walk with God. With all this in place, the Church would have been raising a congregation, society and nation prepared as lambs for their God. Although Church leaders may be limited in being present for the care seekers every time but, by being accessible, they can offer care even when they are not physically present. They can do more in caring when the responsibility is shared and they use God's shepherding model in Psalm 23.

Conclusion

For the Church in Nigeria to fulfil her role in the contemporary time, there is need to keep close to the injunction of God concerning the pastoral ministry as a caring ministry. Without mincing words, leaders and ministers in Christian ministries too cannot but join God in what He is doing in gathering His flock and leading, caring and guiding them. They cannot abdicate their pastoral roles like mercenaries or hired hands, and thus allow the scattered sheep to become prey for wild beasts.

References

- Adams, Arthur M. (1978). *Effective Leadership for Today's Church*. Philadelphia: Westminster press.
- Adeniji, Julius. (2019). "Leadership," *The Minister's Manual: Biblical, Practical, Contemporary, Comprehensive*. Ibadan: Publications Department, NBC, pp. 85-101.
- Adetunji, Oluwaponmile G. (2010). *Leadership in Action: A Source in Church Administration for Students and Ministers*. Ibadan: Baptist Press.
- Ajimatanrareje Sr., Kayode. (1997). *Make Disciples of all Nations: A Handbook for Authentic Christian Ministry*. Ontario: essence Publishing.
- Anthony, Michael J. and James Estep Jr. eds. (2005). *Management Essentials for Christian Ministries*. Nashville: Broadman& Holman Publishers.
- Asumang, Annang. (2010). "The Presence of the Shepherd: A Rhetographic exegesis of Psalm 23," *Conspectus: The Journal of the South African Theological Seminary* Vol. 9. Pp 1-24.
- Audirsch, Jeffrey. (2016). "Psalm 23," *Journal of Baptist Theology and Ministry*. Vol 13, No. 2. pp 59-67.
- Beasley-Murray, Paul. (1995). *A Call to Excellence: An Essential Guide to Christian Leadership*. Britain: Hodder& Stoughton Ltd.
- Borowski, Oded. (2003). *Daily Life in Biblical Time, Archaeology and Biblical Studies*. Atlanta: Society of Biblical Literature.
- Brister, C. W. (1992). *Pastoral Care in the Church* 3rd edition. San Francisco: Harper Collins Publishers.
- Carnes, Philip G. (2007). "Like Sheep without a Shepherd: The Shepherd Metaphor and its Primacy for Biblical Leadership." *Unpublished Thesis of MATS at Reformed Theological Seminary*, Jackson, USA. Pp. 1-66.
- Clebsch, William A. and Charles R. Jaekle. (1975). *Pastoral Care in Historical Perspective*. New York: Aronson.

- Clinebell, Howard. (1991). *Basic Types of Pastoral Care and Counselling: Resources for the Ministry of Healing and Growth*. Nashville: Abingdon Press.
- Dobbins, Gaines S. (1960). *A Ministering Church*. Nashville: Tennessee.
- Eims, LeRoy. (2001). *Be a Motivational Leader*. Benin: Matthew Christian Publications.
- Engstrom, Theodore W. (1977). *The Making of a Christian Leader*. Grand Rapids: Zondervan Publishing House.
- Fernando, Ajith. (1988). *Leadership Lifestyle: A Study of 1 Timothy*. Mumbai: GLS Publishing.
- Genz, William H. ed. (1986). *The Dictionary of Bible and Religion*. Nashville: Abingdon Press.
- Giles, Jere L. and Gefu Jerome. (1990). "Nomads, Ranchers, and the State: The Socio-cultural Aspects of Pastoralism," *The World of Pastoralism: Herding Systems in Comparative Perspectives*, eds. John G. Galaty and L. Johnson Douglas. New York: Guilford. Pp. 100-105.
- Ishola, Simon A. (2019). "Administration/Coordination," *The Minister's Manual: Biblical, Practical, Contemporary, Comprehensive*. Ibadan: Publications Department, NBC, pp. 132-137.
- Ishola, Simon A. and Raphael Olamide Oparinde. (2017). "Leadership Effectiveness and Team Work in a Local Baptist Church," *The Dynamics of Competent Gospel Ministry*, edited by Emiola Nihinlola and Samuel O. Akintola, Ogbomoso: NBTS, pp. 264-277.
- Johnson, Paul E. (1953). *Psychology of Pastoral Care*. Nashville: Abingdon Press.
- Kehinde, Olumide. (2014). *Pastoral Integrity*. Ogbomoso: Hirise Celebrity Publishers.
- Keil, C. F. and F. Delitzsch. (1978). "Psalms," *Commentary on the Old Testament*. Vol. 5 Translated by James Martin. Grand Rapids: William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company.
- Keller, Philip. (1970). *A Shepherd Looks at Psalm 23*. Grand Rapids: Zondervan Publishing House.
- Larson, Bruce, Paul Anderson and Doug Self. (1990). *Mastering Pastoral Care*. Portland: Multnomah Press.
- Maxwell, John C. (2007). *The 21 Irrefutable Laws of Leadership*. Nashville: Thomas Nelson.
- Mosley, Ernest E. (1973). *Called to Joy: Design for Pastoral Ministries*. Nashville: Convention Press.
- Nihinlola, Emiola. (2016). "Shepherding the Flock," *Minister's Manual: Guides for Success in Life and Ministry*. Church Leaders/ Ministers Fellowship of Nigeria. Ilorin: VillaxInc Printers.
- Odewole, Niyi. (2013). *Keys to Success in Shepherd's Preaching/Teaching Ministry*. Kaduna: MODA Digital Services Ltd.
- Oduleye, John. (2015). "Types of Leadership," *The Master Plan of Leadership and Growth*. Kaduna: Radiant prints & Publishers. Pp.52-63.
- Opade, Faith O. (2018). "The Minister and Biblical Concept of Shepherding," *Ministerial Integrity*, Abraham O. Odeleye ed., Ibadan: Kogiah Communications. Pp. 184-195.
- Patterson, Richard. (1992). *Effective Leading: A Guide for all Church Leaders*. Wheaton: Evangelical Training Association.
- Pattison, Stephen. (1993). *A Critique of Pastoral Care* 2nd Edition. London: SPCK.
- Poole, Matthew A. (1962). *A Commentary on the Holy Bible* Vol. II: *Psalms- Malachi*. London: Banner of Truth.
- Porter, Lawrence B. (2001). "Sheep and Shepherd: An Ancient Image of the Church and a Contemporary Challenge," *Gregorianum* Vol. 82, No 1. pp. 51-85.
- Richards, Lawrence O. and Clyde Hoeldtke. (1982). *A Theology of Church Leadership*. Grand Rapids: Zondervan Publishing House
- Ross, Allen P. (2001). *Introducing Biblical Hebrew*. Grand Rapids: Baker Academic.
- Ryken, Leland, James C. Wilhoit & Tremper Longman III eds. (1998). "Sheep, Shepherd," *Dictionary of Biblical Imagery*. Illinois: Intervarsity Press. pp. 782-785.
- Steinbron, Melvin J. (1997). *The Lay Driven Church*. Ventura: Regal Books.
- Stowe, Eugene L. (1976). *The Ministry of Shepherding: A Study of pastoral Practice*. Missouri: Beacon Hill Press.
- Tidball, Derek. (1986). *Skillful Shepherds*. Leicester: Inter-varsity Press.
- White, Peter. (1998). *The Effective Pastor*. Kaduna: Evangel Publication.
- Wise, Carroll. (1966). *The Meaning of Pastoral Care*. New York: Harper and Row.